

FREE-SPACE TIME AND FREQUENCY TRANSFER

Nathan R. Newbury¹, Jean-Daniel Deschenes², Laura C. Sinclair¹, Fabrizio R. Giorgetta¹, William C. Swann¹,
Esther Baumann¹, Hugo Bergeron¹, Michael Cermak¹, Ian Coddington¹

¹National Institute of Standards and Technology, 325 Broadway, Boulder, Colorado 80305

²Université Laval, 2375 rue de la Terrasse, Québec, Québec, Canada, G1V 3Y7
nathan.newbury@nist.gov

Abstract: The rapid advance in optical clocks and oscillators calls for similar advances in free-space frequency/time transfer. I will discuss our frequency-comb based system for coherent optical transfer of time and frequency over free-space links with femtosecond level stabilities and with robustness to atmospheric turbulence.

Introduction

Optical oscillators/clocks can reach timing stabilities of femtoseconds with absolute accuracies approaching the 10^{-18} level [1–4]. As such, they can potentially enable far-reaching applications in precision navigation, positioning, geodesy and phased-array receiver/transmitter as well as tests of relativity. However, many of these applications would require a network of optical clocks/oscillators whose frequency and timing information is compared and possibly synchronized at residual uncertainty levels well below that of the clocks/oscillators themselves. As a simple example, one can envision a single master optical atomic clock that serves as the timescale for a series of slaved optical oscillators located at remote nodes. Current RF based time and frequency transfer systems cannot achieve the stability or accuracy in either frequency or time to match state-of-the-art optical clocks.

Here I will discuss a frequency-comb based technique that enables optical two-way time-frequency transfer over free-space paths [5]. The approach can be used to compare the frequencies of two remote optical clocks/oscillators and in a larger system can support their full synchronization at femtosecond levels [6]. The technique relies on the reciprocity of a single-mode free-space link to cancel out the path length variations due to turbulence at the femtosecond level. Moreover, since it measures time intervals, rather than frequency, it is insensitive to fades of the free space link caused by turbulence-induced scintillation.

Optical two-way time-frequency transfer

To demonstrate optical two-way time frequency transfer, we have conducted a series of experiments on the NIST Boulder campus across a 4-km folded link. The two sites are connected by a single-mode optical link across a turbulent 4-km long air, but are located next to each other to permit a parallel direct comparison (for truth data). Turbulence and platform motion cause strong signal fading and variations in the link propagation delay [7]. In addition, in some experiments, we purposefully vary the overall link distance from a few meters, to 2 km, to 4 km by adjusting the folded path geometry in real time.

In its simplest configuration, the system compares the frequency of the optical clocks/oscillators at the two sites. At each site, the system measures the effective time interval transmitted from the opposite site. The difference in these time intervals provides a measure of the relative frequency between the two clocks/oscillators, following the basic approach of two-way time-frequency transfer. However, here the time interval measurements are made through a linear optical sampling technique via coherent frequency combs in order to achieve femtosecond level precision and accuracy. Figure 1a shows an example of the measured residual frequency noise (modified Allan deviation). As shown, the system can achieve low residual frequency noise even in the presence of significant fades across the link due to atmospheric turbulence. Figure 1b shows the accuracy of the transfer; there is no measurable bias in the system so that it can also support the high accuracy of state-of-the-art optical atomic clocks.

We have exploited this basic technique in a much larger and more complex system in order to fully synchronize to remote clocks [6]. To achieve this synchronization, three systems run in parallel: a coherent signal-mode optical link with a pseudo-random binary sequence (PRBS) modulation for “coarse” synchronization to $\ll 1$ ns, a two-way coherent exchange of optical frequency comb pulses for fine synchronization to < 1 fsec [5], and a coherent optical communication link to send data between the

sites. The coarse PRBS and fine comb-based synchronization both rely on the optical two-way transfer method that in turn rests on the reciprocity of a single mode link across turbulent atmosphere. The resulting synchronization is achieved on the slaved optical frequency comb pulse train, as verified by interference between the master and slave pulse trains at the reference plane. The system produces optical outputs that can be viewed as analogous to the timing outputs of a GPS receiver; the 200-MHz optical pulse train of the frequency comb replaces the 10 MHz rf output and a gated single comb pulse replaces the 1 PPS rf signal.

Figure 1. Example data for frequency comparisons using optical two-way time-frequency transfer. (a) Two-way Modified Allan deviation for 4 km link for 90% link availability (dark blue triangles) and 72% link availability (green triangles) and for a “shorted path” (light blue circles). In addition, the red open squares show the residual stability for the 2 km link measurement described in Ref. [1]. (b) Fractional offset for 8 datasets (circles) and a linear fit (dashed line). The fit gives an offset of $-5.4 \times 10^{-20} \pm 1.9 \times 10^{-19}$, which is consistent with zero as expected, demonstrating a lack of a bias.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated the ability to compare and furthermore synchronization between remote optical oscillators using two-way exchange of light over a free-space link. The overall system is complex but robust, operating unattended for hours at a time. By relying on the reciprocity of a free-space single-mode link, the system can support frequency comparisons with residual frequency instabilities well below the absolute frequency instability of optical clocks for timescales longer than 1 second. It can also support timing deviations of below 1 femtosecond for a synchronized system. This approach should enable future networks of cross-synchronized optical clocks.

References

1. C.W. Chou, D.B. Hume, J.C.J. Koelemeij, D.J. Wineland, T. Rosenband, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **104**, 070802 (2010).
2. N. Hinkley, J.A. Sherman, N.B. Phillips, M. Schioppa, N.D. Lemke, K. Beloy, M. Pizzocaro, C.W. Oates, A.D. Ludlow, *Science*. **341**, 1215 (2013).
3. I. Ushijima, M. Takamoto, M. Das, T. Ohkubo, H. Katori, *Nat. Photonics*. **9**, 185 (2015).
4. B.J. Bloom, T.L. Nicholson, J.R. Williams, S.L. Campbell, M. Bishof, X. Zhang, W. Zhang, S.L. Bromley, J. Ye, *Nature*. **506**, 71 (2014).
5. F.R. Giorgetta, W.C. Swann, L.C. Sinclair, E. Baumann, I. Coddington, N.R. Newbury, *Nat. Photonics*. **7**, 434 (2013).
6. J.D. Deschênes et al., Synchronization of optical oscillators over a free-space link at the femtosecond level, in: *CLEO Postdeadline*, OSA, n.d.
7. L.C. Sinclair, F.R. Giorgetta, W.C. Swann, E. Baumann, I. Coddington, N.R. Newbury, *Phys. Rev. A*. **89**, 023805 (2014).